

Large-scale computing opportunities and challenges

A report from a Supercomputing Task Force for BBSRC and MRC

This report was written by a group of independent experts set up in collaboration between BBSRC and MRC and asked to provide recommendations on strategy for BBSRC and MRC, and for UKRI more generally, to meet challenges and develop opportunities for large-scale computing across bioscience research. The report was completed at the end of 2022 so does not reflect on more recent developments in the landscape.

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Contents

Foreword	3
1. Executive Summary	4
2. Background	6
3. Thematic action areas and recommendations	9
4. Horizon Scanning	24
References	26
Annex 1 – Task Force member affiliations	30
Annex 2 – Examples of DRI community engagement	32
Annex 3 – HECBioSim consortium report	34
Annex 4 – Biophysics and biosimulation community event report	36
Annex 5 – Crick Institute Research computing resources	39

Foreword

Large-scale computing is providing new ways to investigate and understand biological systems, ranging from identifying DNA changes that cause cancer, to developing new drugs, to understanding ecosystems and tackling food shortages. Simulations can provide not only detailed understanding, but predictive models, of biological systems and effects of the environment on them. The value of large-scale computing was clearly demonstrated in the COVID-19 pandemic: some of the most powerful computers in the UK and in the world were used to understand how the SARS-CoV-2 virus infects cells, how it is passed through the air, identify new ways to combat it, and analyse emerging variants. This required a wide range of computational resources and hardware, from traditional high performance computing to applications of the cloud, modification and development of existing state-of-the-art software, and expert computational scientists working together internationally to share models and data. It involved simulation and modelling, and analysis of different types of biological data. Large-scale computation is increasingly integral to biological and biomedical research. There are tremendous opportunities offered by the combination of powerful computing with analysis of biological and medical data, applying artificial intelligence and machine learning.

The UK has not always had an integrated approach to large-scale computing, and bioscience has not always been fully involved in its development and application in the UK. As UKRI works to bring together Research Councils, and coordinate national research strategy, it is developing a coordinated approach to research computing and digital infrastructure. This emphasises the need for long-term investment to deliver coherent, state-of-the-art digital research infrastructure, to enable UK researchers and innovators to harness emerging technology. This infrastructure is essential to maintain and develop UK scientific research, and so in turn is vital for UK health, security and prosperity.

UKRI's ambitions present an opportunity to the Research Councils and the communities that they represent. UKRI has a user-focused strategy and aims to build infrastructure that meets the existing and future ambitions of researchers and innovators. To enable this, community needs must be articulated and understood to influence development and build an ecosystem they can harness effectively. This should span a range of computational resources at

different scales, including large scale computing, and infrastructure to store, curate and exploit research data. Data science applications in biological and biomedical sciences offer enormous potential, but some involve additional complexity (e.g. personal data). The confluence of data science and large-scale computation promises significant progress and impact. Together, these emphasise the breadth of requirements in designing enabling the UK digital research infrastructure (DRI). It is also important to consider the need to build diversity, and to plan flexibility to be able to meet rapidly evolving community needs. The DRI should provide a broad range of computing and data capabilities, support requirements, system types and computer architectures.

The Task Force and this report seek to advise and shape MRC and BBSRC strategies for the design and development of the DRI, and associated services and essential skills, across the research landscape, and in an international context. The experience of domain experts has been used to identify essential characteristics of a successful computational research ecosystem – vitally, including the human dimension and elements within it – and to make recommendations to BBSRC and MRC, and more broadly to UKRI and policy makers about how these should be developed to maintain and grow UK strength in bioscience research.

The Task Force identified the following thematic areas, describing the needs and challenges, and made recommendations for action in each:

- Cohesion and Join Up
- Diversity and Flexibility
- Community Needs
- Cloud
- Exascale
- Software
- People, Skills and Training
- Sustainability

I would like to thank the expert group who informed and developed this report, the secretariat who supported us throughout and the computational researchers and specialists, from academic and industry, who provided insights throughout the process.

Professor Adrian Mulholland – Chair of the Joint BBSRC-MRC Supercomputing Task Force

1. Executive Summary

The Task Force made a series of recommendations to advise and inform BBSRC, MRC and UKRI strategies. These highlight specific requirements of biological and biomedical (also referred to as bioscience in this report) research and researchers. They also emphasise the need and opportunities to work with the development and implementation of the UKRI DRI strategy, to ensure that the DRI meets the research needs of bioscience, and that these communities can harness the full power of modern digital platforms, tools, techniques and skills to deliver impact for the UK.

Cohesion and joined up environment

Recommendations focus on building a coordinated and joined-up DRI, integrating the needs of biological and biomedical researchers, attract applications from new areas, improve efficiency of resource use, reduce barriers to use, and encourage best practice.

Recommendation 1: UKRI, BBSRC and MRC should ensure research community requirements guide the implementation of Digital Research Infrastructure, seeking to build a more coherent landscape

Recommendation 2: UKRI should support increased coordination across large-scale computing and data facilities, projects and planning (e.g. through the DRI strategy)

Recommendation 3: UKRI, BBSRC and MRC should engage with research communities and international partners to incentivise development of software and standards, and to embed best practice in research and infrastructure

Diversity and Flexibility

The best scientific research requires diversity in every sense, bringing different skills, knowledge and insight, and the ability to work across disciplines. Biological and biomedical research needs a diverse and flexible DRI, encompassing a range of architectures, to meet

wide-ranging and evolving needs and respond to shifting demands and emerging threats (e.g. new pathogen) and opportunities.

Recommendation 4: BBSRC and MRC, working with UKRI, should ensure that the diverse needs of biological and biomedical communities are considered during the development and implementation of UKRI's DRI strategy

Community Needs

Discusses the challenge of maintaining an up to date understanding of biological and biomedical researcher requirements and the opportunities to engage with community representatives.

Recommendation 5: BBSRC and MRC should include large-scale computing in research strategy, planning and assessment. BBSRC and MRC should develop and carry out programmes of continuous community engagement to understand and record research computing needs, build knowledge bases and maintain expertise

Recommendation 6: Research Councils should work with their communities to develop and use a common language to understand and describe scientific communities' computing usage

Cloud

Discusses applications of, and opportunities presented by, cloud computing in biological and biomedical research. The recommendations advocate for a cross-UKRI coordinated strategy for the use of cloud computing, informed by UK and international expertise and experience of relevant research applications.

Recommendation 7: UKRI should develop a strategy around the deployment, provision and use of centralised, local and commercial cloud research computing infrastructure as an integrated part of the UK's computing infrastructure

Exascale

Describes the evolution of large-scale computing towards exascale for applications in biological and biomedical research. The recommendations centre around the need for investment towards an exascale ecosystem in the UK.

Recommendation 8: UKRI, working with BBSRC and MRC, should engage with biological and biomedical research communities to understand current and anticipated large-scale computing requirements and opportunities, including potential exascale applications. For developing large scale computing strategy and capability, cross-domain collaboration across UKRI is vital. Engagement with, and awareness of, international efforts towards exascale development and application is also essential

Software

Discusses the importance of software for research and the challenges of developing and maintaining software. The recommendations call for recognition of, and strategy for, supporting bioscience research software development, engineering and sustainability.

Recommendation 9: BBSRC and MRC should work with other funders (including other UKRI Research Councils, Wellcome, CZI, Gates, Cancer Research UK, other charities and international partners etc) to create a cohesive framework supporting the life-cycle of software, including development, engineering, sustainability and maintenance, for large-scale computing in biological and biomedical research

Recommendation 10: BBSRC and MRC should map research software used by their communities/ research areas

People, Skills and Training

Highlights the importance of and shortages in skills/ professionals needed to support research using large-scale computing. These recommendations advocate understanding and supporting the training requirements of users, and the careers of computational experts.

Recommendation 11: BBSRC and MRC should engage with their communities to understand requirements and develop computational training strategies

Recommendation 12: BBSRC and MRC should encourage recognition and support of the careers of computational experts including software and data engineers

Sustainability

Discusses the challenge of funding sustainability for the large-scale computing ecosystem. The recommendations focus on building consistent, easy and continuous access to core resources, enabling researchers to plan long-term and prioritise innovative science.

Recommendation 13: UKRI and Research Councils should refine funding mechanisms to improve the sustainability of funding for core DRI

UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure thematic areas

Figure 1: Task Force report themes aligned to UKRI digital research infrastructure themes

2. Background

2.1. Introduction

Large-scale computing (LSC) has transformed research. By harnessing the explosion in data and rapidly improving technologies, researchers have used large-scale computing to investigate critical questions, advance the frontiers of discovery and improve human health. Large-scale computing has been a vital tool for understanding the infection mechanisms of COVID-19,¹ mutations associated with cancer², investigating food security³ and modelling ecosystem services⁴. Across the COVID-19 pandemic HPC enabled researchers to use multiscale computational microscopy to interrogate aerosols and update models of airborne transmission (figure 2), use large language models to understand genomic data and refine the identification, classification and prediction of Covid variants (figure 3) and simulate aerosols to provide detailed analysis of transmission risks in different scenarios (figure 4).

Prior to the formation of UKRI in 2017, much UK investment in HPC aligned with the strategy and needs of individual Research Councils and their associated research communities, with some notable cross-Council initiatives (institutional, e.g. university, investments in HPC should also be noted as a significant part of the UK landscape). While this model helped to build a diverse, requirements-driven UK digital research infrastructure (DRI), the formation of UKRI provides an opportunity to work across research communities and disciplines, and to develop a cohesive landscape for large-scale computing. UKRI's ambitions include the development of joined-up provisioning of HPC services and DRI, enabling UK researchers and innovators to make the most of technological advances and new opportunities.

UKRI's DRI strategy outlines ambitions to provide the UK research and innovation community with access to world-class computing infrastructure across different levels, types and scales up to national large-scale capability. The strategy includes plans for delivering a coherent state-of-the-art national DRI⁵ in the next 5–10 years, building on extensive reviews of the UK

research infrastructure landscape as published in UKRI's opportunity report⁶ and landscape analysis⁷. The UKRI DRI strategy is led by user needs and aims to harness the increasingly heterogeneous systems, novel architectures and convergence of traditionally distinct systems and workflows. Research Councils have an opportunity to align their own computational resource provisioning strategies with and through UKRI and to represent their communities' needs in implementation of the UKRI strategy. This will ensure that UK researchers are able to harness the full power of the modern digital platforms, tools, techniques and skills that UKRI aims to develop. This report describes recommendations on LSC needs from BBSRC and MRC research community representatives, who formed the joint BBSRC-MRC supercomputing Task Force.

In the past, biomedical and biological researchers, have made up a relatively small proportion of UK LSC users. This is changing, with the ever-increasing generation and use of large datasets for research. Bioscience research increasingly involve computationally intensive techniques, modelling, and processing of data on large scales. Data transfer alone is becoming a significant demand in many workflows. Biological and biomedical research communities are applying significant computing power to a variety of research questions, including epistatic genome-wide association studies⁸, pathogenicity⁹, drug design¹⁰, macroscale ecology¹¹ and disease transmission¹². Over 50 % of BBSRC responsive mode grants now involve large-scale biological data, more than doubling between 2008 and 2018¹³. However, biological and biomedical science computing workflows are not always suited to traditional HPC architectures, hindering their application on large-scale computing systems. As the UK seeks to develop the next generation of computing capabilities, a step change is needed in the way biological and biomedical researchers are represented in DRI planning and development. It will be important to consider issues of access and use of scientific computing resources and services.

HPC performance continues to grow rapidly and the most recent addition to the TOP500 project¹⁴ list of the most powerful non-distributed computer systems has achieved exascale performance. It is UKRI's ambition is to develop a pathway to an exascale ecosystem for the UK by the middle of this decade. Two strategic outline business cases are under review¹⁵. UKRI is also funding initiatives to understand and deliver the next generation of HPC infrastructure, through initiatives such as the ExCALIBUR research Programme¹⁶ and Tier 2 HPC investment. Exascale computing was one of the principal areas of advice sought by BBSRC and MRC when setting up the Task Force; however, the group recommended that discussions on exascale should be contextualized within the wider landscape. The Task Force stressed the need for the for diverse and flexible compute resources for bioscience research. Diverse HPC architecture is a key piece of this landscape. Developing HPC applications is essential to prepare for exascale. Computer architecture describes the structure of a computing system and how its components, both hardware and software, interact and work together¹⁷. HPC systems tend to encompass multiple functional components, requiring decision making when designing system architecture¹⁵. While all HPC systems are designed for high performance, different jobs, for example GPU enable or storage intensive workloads, will run more efficiently with particular components and system architecture, and it is important to understand user requirements in system planning and development.

Historically, the UK has been a pioneer in the field of computing and, driven by innovative mathematicians, scientists, engineers and communication specialists. The UK has made important technological leaps through developments including the Difference Engine, the Small-Scale Experimental Machine and Ferranti Mark 1¹⁸. ARM-based supercomputing has recently become a reality. UK HPC for scientific research has encompassed a range of technologies across different scales of computing power from 'international-leadership class' systems, such as ARCHER2, to local systems within institutions, including university-level HPC. National provision has been supported by Research Councils and now UKRI, and this has included co-funding with Government and University partners such as the development of DIRAC, investment in large-scale computing at specific centres such as Cirrus or Cambridge Service for Data Driven Discovery (CSD3) and joint council investments such as HECToR (the last national HPC service that BBSRC directly invested in), and/or partnering with organisations such as the Met Office. In 2020 UKRI began investing in infrastructure through The World Class Labs funding scheme¹⁹, including funds for enhancing Tier-2 HPC capabilities for machine learning, DIRAC capabilities and JASMIN data analytics.

While UK bioscience research within BBSRC and MRC remits historically did not involve much intensive HPC use, and such research received little support from these Councils, large-scale computing applications in bioscience have grown internationally and more recently in the UK also. Much work in the UK biosciences domain has focused on modest to high throughput, and complexity computing, which has been supported locally by universities, or targeted funding to consortia for building bespoke systems. While it was historically difficult for UK biological and biomedical researchers to access national supercomputing facilities, they are now increasingly able to use Tier 1 HPC resources (ARCHER2) and the middle-Tier computational resources supported through other Research Councils, such as the EPSRC-funded Tier 2 facilities; the next phase of Tier 2 systems will be UKRI supported, and so open to researchers from across Council remits, which is a good example of cross-Council coordination by UKRI in HPC. BBSRC and MRC also invest in large-scale computing through their Institutes, Units and Centres^{20, 21}. Institute digital research support and infrastructure is tailored to their individual strategy. Investments include CPU or GPU clusters, high performance data storage, local software expertise for installation or development, virtual machines, workflow optimisation, cloud infrastructure, advanced analytic expertise, database management and domain specific support.

One of the areas UKRI plans to harness is the vast potential of artificial intelligence (AI), with ambitions to support world-leading AI innovation and ensure that the UK has the right environment for AI researchers and innovators to thrive²². AI describes computational tools and technologies that seek to replicate human intelligence to tackle complex tasks, including learning, problem solving and image analysis. AI has already had profound in bioscience research, including discovery science to better understand disease²³, prognosis²⁴, and prevention²⁵, drug discovery, development, repurposing and clinical trials²⁶, conservation strategies²⁷, improving agricultural efficiency, yields and costs²⁸ and antibiotic resistance²⁹. Applications and impact of advanced analytics and AI in research continue to increase, driven by computing capabilities and data availability. With access to suitable DRI, UK bioscience researchers are well positioned to play a leading role in harnessing these opportunities.

MRC and BBSRC worked with the Task Force to better understand the computing needs of the research communities that they support, to inform the development and implementation of a strategy for investment and support in this area. This will complement ongoing Research Council, UKRI and community-led DRI initiatives.

2.2. Approach

To understand bioscience research computing needs (including associated training, skills, software and services) of the research communities that they support, BBSRC and MRC formed a Task Force of experts (Annex 1), chaired by Professor Adrian Mulholland, to inform and help shape the development and implementation of a strategy for investment and support in this area. Task Force members provided advice from their individual perspectives, but also endeavoured to represent their wider communities, including identifying and providing links with communities, and knowledge of the national and international context, to identify current and future needs, and make recommendations to address challenges and opportunities.

Through a series of discussions and meetings, and by bringing together its members' disparate expertise and awareness of different research communities, the Task Force sought to define strategic priorities and recommendations, drawing out common themes, which were used to structure and develop this report.

2.3. Aims

The report draws on the experience of Task Force members, BBSRC and MRC staff, and community engagement. It is not a comprehensive review of the computing infrastructure landscape in biological and biomedical research, nor a detailed mapping of UK computing infrastructure.

This report aims to:

- Provide an overview of the needs, challenges, and opportunities of LSC for biological and biomedical research in the UK, and highlight areas where action is required
- Advise and inform MRC and BBSRC (and UKRI) strategies for the provision of the type and scale of computational resource, and associated services and skills across the BBSRC and MRC remits, within UKRI and wider UK and international partnerships
- Inform other stakeholders, such as policy makers, by providing understanding of the relevance of LSC, and inform actions to improve synergy across the UK research computing landscape, and build partnerships
- Compile qualitative insights to build understanding of the objectives, likely direction, and impacts of ongoing/new investments in computing infrastructure and opportunities to strengthen alignment across initiatives.

The report references evidence and stakeholders, and outlines opportunities for engagement, in the UK and internationally, and the need for a framework for stakeholder mapping and community engagement. We stress the need for UK bioscience to be equipped to seize the opportunities offered by LSC, and for bioscience to be integral in strategy and planning .

The Task Force highlighted case studies demonstrating the impact of (large-scale) computing on research, international competition, and opportunities in the next 10 years, and the threats to UK research in the crucial bioscience sector, of international isolation, of failing to support LSC for UK researchers, failing to support the specific needs of computational science, and from a lack of integration of bioscience in the development of LSC in the UK.

2.4. Scope

This report centres on the needs, challenges, and opportunities for LSC in UK bioscience research. It also highlights the importance of the wider digital research infrastructure, and the need for bioscience to be integrated in its planning, development and implementation. Our recommendations highlight opportunities for cohesion across biological and biomedical research, and with the wider UKRI DRI.

It also seeks to consider the importance of computing for research "from laptop to exascale" in its recommendations. Supercomputing infrastructure is used in this document as an umbrella term for a range of systems from HPC, to cloud, specialised clusters, emerging architectures and the path towards exascale computing. Also, where appropriate, it includes associated data infrastructure, services, software and skills, which are essential intertwined components of the wider digital research ecosystem; large-scale data storage is growing rapidly and is both an associated need and opportunity for LSC.

The Task Force identified the following thematic action areas, which constitute the main sections of the report, and focus the description of the needs, challenges, and recommendations:

1. Cohesion and Join Up
2. Diversity and Flexibility
3. Community Needs
4. Cloud
5. Exascale
6. Software
7. People, Skills and Training
8. Sustainability

3. Thematic action areas and recommendations

3.1. Coherent and joined up environment

Theme summary, challenges, and implications for research

HPC is increasingly important in biological and biomedical research.^{9,10,11,25,30} It is essential that the UK DRI provides bioscience with access to internationally competitive HPC resources. The Task Force advocates the development of coordinated and joined-up DRI across biological and biomedical communities and across the UKRI remit. This will enable efficient use of UK resources and facilitate work across disciplines, as previously recognised in the Government Office for Science Report *Large-scale computing: the case for greater UK coordination*.

The UKRI DRI Strategy, the Government Office for Science Report³¹, BBSRC's review of data-intensive bioscience¹³ and the Australian Research Data Commons framework³², all call for greater collaboration and coordination of research infrastructure planning to improve researcher access to resources and improve efficiency. Building a coherent environment requires understanding of UK's DRI across different research communities to define how these resources or associated services could work collaboratively. The Task Force anticipates that a cohesive landscape would bring widespread benefits for research, including:

- Greater efficiency, including pooling or sharing of resources and services
- Improved understanding of community use, including common requirements, need and barriers
- Better infrastructure planning and policy development;
- Stronger linkage to the NHS and alignment of health/data strategies across non-departmental public bodies, research organisations and government

- Better linkage of local and national data would make the UK an attractive partner for international initiatives
- Improved information for the identification of skills, software, expertise or services required by multiple communities, gaps or skill shortages and opportunities to address challenges across disciplines
- Simplification of access to resources and lower entry barriers for new users
- Aiding collaborations, international partnerships, and new ways of working.

Recommendations

Recommendation 1: UKRI, BBSRC and MRC should ensure research communities requirements guide the implementation of Digital Research Infrastructure, seeking to build a more coherent landscape

The Task Force advocates collaboration and coordination, informed by research community needs, to deliver a coherent UK DRI to enable cutting-edge research and innovation. A coherent landscape should maximise usability, improve efficiency, generate greater return on investment and avoid duplication. Improved coherence across UKRI should give economies of scale and promote for cross-disciplinary working. The UKRI DRI Strategy should be implemented in consultation with Research Councils to ensure community needs and challenges guide its development. It should identify commonalities across Research Council communities, opportunities to increase coherence of existing UKRI infrastructure, with regional and national efforts, while setting requirements for a programme of sustained investment to maintain UK competitiveness.

Research Councils should act to understand system usage across their communities, to support joined-up and efficient provision of research computing

infrastructure across UKRI. This should include the DRI needs of users across computing scales, from wet labs to LSC. Best practice developed in UK centres of excellence can be made accessible by embedding portability in design, coding and workflows.

The governance structure supporting the delivery of UKRI's DRI Strategy should be diverse in all senses and should include professional technologists. Core academic/technologist oversight could exist within the delivery team of the "Foundational Tools and Techniques" theme with governance linking them to the relevant packages across other themes and a clear remit, an experienced, credible, consensus-building Chair and representative expert members from across different research disciplines supported by the UKRI Research Councils. Technologist oversight, with a UKRI-wide view, should inform investment in underpinning and enabling aspects of DRI, e.g., connectivity, digital identity, single sign-in across infrastructures, multi-factor authentication (MFA), billing and resource allocation. Initial proof-of-concept integration examples should be sought to find cost benefits.

UKRI's join-up efforts should align with, and complement, a sustained national investment plan for the UK computing ecosystem, including software and skills, as highlighted in the GO Science report²⁹. This will grow a cost-effective and sustainable research computing ecosystem in the UK, investing in a wide range of computing architectures based on user need. The ongoing work of the Task Force enabled them to rapidly respond to a DCMS call for evidence to support their future of compute review in October 2022, providing a combined answer incorporating a view from a range of expertise.

Recommendation 2: UKRI should use the DRI strategy to support increased coordination across large-scale computing facilities and reduce research barriers

The UKRI DRI Strategy implementation is an opportunity to set a culture that prioritises harmony in DRI development, drawing out the benefits of resource coordination. Building commonalities in resource allocation, optimal machine assignment and single login authentication, access, accounting infrastructure (AAAI) could simplify access to resources, reduce the administrative burden on researchers and support new users. Greater interoperability and coordination between sites/facilities will facilitate collaboration. It will also facilitate coupling of codes across different or heterogeneous machines and software optimisation for different architectures.

Harmonisation across Research Council investments provides an opportunity to address common barriers

faced by researchers, e.g. in accessing underpinning services and support; differences between application processes for different systems; shortages in technical and computing expertise/training; and funding for software sustainability and maintenance. Insufficient support for Linux workstations in research organisations is a barrier to LSC use, because HPC machines and much of the open-source software for visualising and processing HPC data use Linux. The application processes for accessing large-scale computing systems vary, with differing technical assessments, software requirements, etc. Streamlined access could begin to mitigate these challenges, but would need to account for different user requirements, including allocations for large collaborative group projects with multiple users as well as single user applications. There have been efforts within UKRI to harmonise application mechanisms, e.g. the EPSRC Tier 2 Access to High Performance Computing Panel. UKRI can build on this, simplify access to LSC and enable researchers to spend more of their time on science.

The Task Force proposes specific mechanisms to encourage new users to access LSC, including lightweight application processes for small amounts of resource, with access to funded support and technical expertise. Community groups, including High-End Computing consortiums³³, Collaborative Computational Projects³⁴, the EU's BioExcel³⁵ and CompBioMed³⁶ Centres of Excellence, provide support for new and more experienced users and could be leveraged to understand potential support mechanisms. Support for entry level users is undertaken alongside supporting the whole community, and where user need exceeds support capacity, the specialists who manage HPC clusters are having to spend more time teaching rudimentary skills to new users, reducing capacity for other elements of their role. Additional support for new users would develop community skills and provide more capacity.

Recommendation 3: UKRI, BBSRC and MRC should engage with communities to incentivise standard development, establishing complementary systems to embed best practice in research and infrastructure

Community standards help a research field to progress as a whole, supporting reliability and interoperability. Biological and biomedical sciences have demonstrated excellent capacity to standardise and collaborate to enable global research: examples include the Protein Data Bank, Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive and European Bioinformatics Institute databases. Working with communities, Research Councils should continue to develop policies on software standards and data sharing, and mechanisms to support best practice.

Organisations such as the Collaborative Computational Projects³⁷, High End Computing (HEC) Consortia, ELIXIR-Europe and The Software Sustainability Institute³⁸, have led and are leading community building projects, setting standards and setting best practice in areas of bioscience. These organisations have been very successful in building cohesive communities, and provide opportunities to learn factors for success in building standards and best practice. Barriers to the development of data standards in bioscience can include an absence of leadership, lack of standard ownership, and limited community uptake¹³. Trusted Research Environments (TREs) will need to define and standardize levels of security needed for different classes of data, e.g. clinical data/patient records. The UKRI road map should identify standards that should be developed to build a joined-up user environment and mechanisms to support best practice. Accompanying UKRI policy should promote participation of UK researchers in international standard development. Collaborative

projects, e.g. ELIXIR and EHDEN, allow research communities to develop international standards, as well as shared software and training, and can provide access to data, tools, analysis workflows and computing resource. Potential opportunities include funding fundamental DRI as part of hardware expenditure, incorporating DRI into applications and funding decisions.

The Task Force discussed the opportunity for funders to provide greater support for applicants and funding Panels/Boards via policies or best practice guides. These would seek to bring initiatives into existing infrastructure and build on efforts to develop a cohesive environment. Cross-council guidance should set clear expectations for applicants, expected panel expertise, and criteria for assessing infrastructure elements of applications. Guidance could range from advisory principles to architectural patterns including data security, interoperability, reproducibility and output/data management. Important considerations include access, governance and FAIR principles.

Figure 2: Large-scale computation reveals the behaviour of the SARS-CoV-2 virus in a respiratory aerosol particle. A range of computational HPC and cloud resources were applied, in multiscale simulations. Simulations of the particle included a billion atoms. Using these simulations, other methods modelled the opening of the viral spike protein and the effect of pH changes on it, important for understanding airborne transmission.¹² A summary lecture is also available on [YouTube](#).

3.2. Diversity and Flexibility

Theme summary, challenges, and implications for research

There is a diversity of user needs across the UK biological and biomedical research and a scarcity of deeper community specific information to meaningfully capture these and translate them into compute-related requirements/demand. The compute needs of biological and biomedical researchers, span from use of desk-top computers to use of national large-scale computing services. Furthermore, there is an increasing need for on-demand, short-term episodic/intermittent access to large-scale computing capabilities. Facilitating this variety of use and access types requires a diverse and flexible environment, and a range of architectures, including the ability to use heterogenous architectures (e.g. CPUs and GPUs) in a single workflow. Flexible systems are required to accommodate shifting needs, for instance the development of new techniques/datasets requiring greater capacity or capabilities. Both the GO Science report on Large-Scale Computing³¹ and the BBSRC-led Scientific Computing in the Biosciences workshop³⁹ (2021) but also through other engagement with these research communities have reached the same conclusion (i.e. that current and potential users need the system to have a diverse range of capability, support requirements, system sizes and architecture.

The diverse needs of biological and biomedical researchers include specific digital and infrastructure requirements based on the type of data and use, e.g. sensitive data for health research. TREs are being developed to provide secure and timely access to sensitive data, to researchers from trusted research organisations. TRE systems are not openly accessible, so, by design, data cannot openly travel into and out of the environment. This in turn influences large-scale computing architecture requirements. Understanding specific community needs during scoping, planning and development is important for maximizing value from investments and involving different research areas.

Intermittent access to large-scale compute was a key need identified through the emerging findings of the UKRI DARE UK⁴⁰ digital research infrastructure programme to support the needs and identify the requirements in using complex sensitive data across disciplines and sector. One of the key challenges to be addressed on irregular demand from the sensitive data research community is how to leverage large-scale compute capacity (HPC or HTC) while maintaining the security of the data itself, which has not traditionally been a consideration for large-scale compute environments. There are options to address this need, including the provisioning of non-traditional large-scale capability through cloud resources via an

on-demand model, traditional large-scale computing is likely to remain on premises in the near and medium future (see also cloud section).

Recommendations

Recommendation 4: BBSRC and MRC, working with UKRI, should ensure that the diverse needs of biological and biomedical communities are considered during the implementation of UKRI's DRI strategy

Implementation of the UKRI DRI Strategy should be informed by the requirements of research communities within and across Research Council remits. Effective engagement should be brokered by Research Councils consulting their communities, with clear mechanisms to feed research needs, opportunities and threats into the implementation of UKRI DRI, utilising community groups, scoping projects (e.g. DARE UK) and community experts (e.g. EPSRC's Tier 2 Discussion group). This should be an integral part of UK research strategy and planning, at all levels and for the long term, not confined to one-off consultations (e.g. to inform investments in the short term). Recommendation 5 discusses Research Council community engagement. Future needs of biological and biomedical research communities are likely to be evolve rapidly and different from the current state of the art, necessitating different types of architectures and the removal of silos between disciplines. UKRI, BBSRC and MRC should work with research communities to identify key workflows and requirements required – for example, to facilitate development towards an exascale environment, to data-intensive workflows or enabling the use of integrated CPU and GPUs workflows.

3.3. Community Needs

Theme summary, challenges, and implications for research

One of the major challenges with building biological and biomedical computing capability is understanding the current, emerging and future requirements of the diverse research communities, spanning areas as diverse as genomic, clinical information, imaging, macro-ecology and multiscale simulation. The Task Force noted various evidence/requirement gathering activities to understand community needs, which were useful in developing our recommendations. We also noted that many of these were one-off exercises. There is a need for computational requirements to be an ongoing and integral part of planning research infrastructure and strategy. Community engagement in assessing computational needs should be regular, integral and long-term in research planning, not driven only by specific spending plans or

investment opportunities. This includes biological and biomedical contribution to UKRI planning in DRI. Some communities commented that it was not always clear how information how to engage with Councils, and also how information was used to influence Research Council decision making (see Annex 2).

National DRI development should take into account the hardware, software and workflow development and engineering and support requirements of the biosciences. It is essential for the UK that DRI provides infrastructure, services and policies suitable for biological and biomedical research needs, accessible to new and non-traditional users as well as experts. Relevant opportunities and expertise should be identified and incorporated into UKRI DRI planning and implementation. There are also particular requirements for some (e.g. personal) biomedical data that go beyond those for data from most other domains: e.g., the security and privacy considerations required for some medical data developed through investments such as the ISCF Digital Innovation Hubs and NHS England's investments in TRE development and delivery.

Community engagement generated a range of useful insights, ranging from cross-cutting to community specific:

- Access issues, particularly for new and small-scale users, can hinder the uptake and application of research computing (particularly large-scale computing)³¹.
- Data is outscaling the availability of hardware¹³ and a lack of flexible short-term, and of long-term, storage limits the scale of projects in biosimulation (Annex 3) and many other areas, and limits the development of AI/ML and limiting opportunities to extract value from biological and biomedical data.
- The computing and data storage environment must be agile and scalable, suitable for access to and analysis of cross-disciplinary data, including health-related data (anonymised as required)¹³.
- Digital infrastructure should minimize the time spent transferring data and configuring hardware and support the development of best practice, building communities and knowledge exchange³¹. Comparison should be made with international research data infrastructure development.
- There is a rapidly growing and not sufficiently met demand for GPU resource, a feature of 7/10 of the world's top supercomputers, in the UK. While GPUs are available at Tier2 HPC in the UK, UK researchers require greater access to a wide range of computational architectures, including emerging architectures (Annex 3).

Recommendations

Recommendation 5: BBSRC and MRC should include large-scale computing in research strategy, planning and assessment. BBSRC and MRC should develop and carry out programmes of continuous community engagement to understand and record research computing needs, build knowledge bases and maintain expertise.

BBSRC and MRC should engage across their communities to understand community challenges and requirements for shared computing infrastructure, and to identify community-specific requirements not addressed through shared infrastructure. This will inform both Research Councils and UKRI's investments into research computing infrastructure and will improve coordination in planning and provisioning scientific computing infrastructure. Implementing an effective long-term strategy requires continuous community engagement supported by Council resources rather than an intermittent activity collecting snapshots of need. Engagement should build on and amplify efforts to date: Annex 2 includes a list of national and international initiatives.

Community engagement could be aided by the development of common language and frameworks to plan across UKRI and would explore key questions such as access modes, hardware/middleware and workflow requirements, scale, barriers and anticipated needs. This would capture a deeper understanding of how communities are using computing, what services they need and how they could be supported. Computational research should be represented in BBSRC and MRC strategic advisory bodies, in planning and in panels.

Recommendation 6: Research councils should work with their communities to develop and use a common language to understand and describe scientific communities' computing usage

Common language will help develop a better understanding of the commonalities, challenges and opportunities for Research Councils and their communities. It can be challenging to describe HPC use by the biological and biomedical research communities: some of the specific terminology used does not readily translate to other disciplines. Developing a consistent vocabulary will help the Research Councils and UKRI to understand and describe computing use issues and opportunities. Research communities are vital stakeholders in driving the development of common language, and harnessing this opportunity for multi- and interdisciplinary research.

This common language should be supplemented by developing frameworks to describe communities' use

Outline: Using foundation models to predict SARS-CoV-2 evolution

Figure 3: Outline of the training and development of foundational models to investigate the evolution of COVID-19 variants and predict potential mutations, developing biological large language models with 2.5 and 25 billion trainable parameters. This research leveraged several supercomputers to track changes across the whole genome and was nominated for a Gordan Bell Special Prize.⁴¹

of computing and typical use types found in different communities, including infrastructure support needs. The Task Force proposes a framework to scope expertise and resource, which would plot the scale of computing, from desktop to I Tier-1 systems, against associated expertise and research area. For example, this framework would indicate what proportion use local multiprocessors, GPU workstations or clusters, within e.g. the clinical bioinformatics community, and what is their associated computing expertise. This should help build Research Council understanding of and support for research computing across their communities.

3.4. Cloud

Theme summary, challenges, and implications for research

Cloud computing is a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort and service provider interaction. These elements cover the well known services of infrastructure, software and platforms.

The use of cloud computing platforms for research is rapidly evolving and gaining widespread adoption

across a broad range of research domains. In this context we see these cloud computing platforms being run on infrastructure provided by both commercial public cloud providers (AWS, Google, Amazon) and private UKRI cloud resource providers running institutional clouds or community clouds. Thus, here we see clouds used via a Hybrid model with both on-premises usage within an institution for use by that institution owned by that institution and off-premises on infrastructure funded by UKRI but held at another institution and shared or on equipment provided by a commercial cloud provider. The real advantage of cloud computing is not where the computing is run, or how it is paid for, or whether it is high throughput or highly scalable. The real advantage comes from the ability to provide on-demand access to configurable storage, compute, and network infrastructure, combined with shareable data sets and the power to create on-demand customisable software defined research platforms designed for particular research communities. With this enabling cloud middleware software layer supported by common APIs and common infrastructure management methodology allowing ease of execution across a federated cloud infrastructure. This provides research communities the ability to build and share customised research platforms (hardware, data, applications and workflows) and run them on their own infrastructure, across a federation

of private UKRI funded infrastructure or in the public commercial cloud or any combination thereof. Cloud computing also separates control and operation of the infrastructure layer from the science platform layer, which has many benefits in terms of how such platforms are built and operated. Cloud computing models open many technical and operation opportunities when considering how UKRI could develop and operate a centralised shared national DRI. Here one could provide a single federated national shared heterogeneous infrastructure, and then separate infrastructure management from platform management and user support. Allowing UKRI to have community focused science platforms and user support teams running on a single UKRI national cloud infrastructure adopting DevOps working practises.

Examples of cloud computing providers include research organisations, such as CyVerse UK data storage and virtual machines with access to an HPC environment hosted by the BBSRC-funded Earlham Institute⁴², MRC-CLIMB compute, storage, and analysis tools for microbiologists, and commercial companies such as Amazon Web Services (AWS), Oracle, Azure (Microsoft) and Google Cloud. Outside the biosciences, federated community clouds based on on-premises private clouds exist for STFC (JASMIN⁴³ and IRIS⁴⁴). These research on-premises environments distinguish themselves from public clouds as being based on OpenStack, a common and popular environment for research for instantiating private cloud resources which can maintain community specific policies, governance and sovereignty. STFC IRIS is of particular note as this has significantly contributed to the creation of “Scientific OpenStack”; an opinionated research computing environment, which has invested in not only IaaS elements but also created community specific HPC and AI portals to simplify the access to cloud resources and make it possible to instantiate supercomputing class performance⁴⁵ in a software-defined model. Thus, when speaking of “cloud”, this should not be synonymous with Public Cloud, but recognise and encompass an ecosystem of cloud native resources which may comprise a community mission.

For example, the UKRI Scientific OpenStack software digital asset has been under long term development within the UK for the last 6 years, with funding from STFC IRIS, STFC DiRAC, STFC SKA, EPSRC Tier 2 and MRC capital awards from MRC BioStatistics and MRC Epidemiology Units in Cambridge. This has enabled Cambridge and other sites to deploy a UK Cloud middleware layer customised for research that provides one of the UK’s largest HPC systems as a UK public sector cloud with both high throughput and traditional highly scalable supercomputer-like

systems. Furthermore, STFC has just awarded a £7M grant to a consortium of UK Universities to develop the Scientific OpenStack as an integral part of the UK node of the global SKA Science Regional Centre deployment. The SKA is developing OpenStack clouds to deploy and control the computer infrastructure of the telescope and also for the distributed regional federation of compute and storage infrastructure that will enable global scientific analysis of very large volumes of SKA data. We also see a federated OpenStack cloud supporting the large computational needs of the world’s largest high energy physics experiment at CERN.

Cloud-enabled platforms can provide the flexibility and agility need for the diverse and unique needs of biomedical researchers. Historically the biological and biomedical users have used mainly private cloud services. However, public cloud has certain potential benefits (payment model as operational pay-as-you-go vs up front capital, data sharing, access to new technologies not available within an individual institution or with national government funded DRI, turnaround time for large computational workflow, etc) and hence a shift to hybrid cloud solutions including public/commercial cloud solutions is potentially beneficial in certain cases. To support hybrid cloud efficiently however, further abstraction above the level of the infrastructure, the proprietary APIs used in different commercial cloud environments can increase complexity and reduce interoperability. Thus open source⁴⁶ will be a key enabler in hybrid cloud.

The UK DRI strategy includes high-throughput computational infrastructure required for the future of data, including the incorporation of cloud computing. Cloud computing can enable users, via platforms, without the technical skills to develop code or use large systems to access more high-throughput computational systems/approaches. Adoption of cloud services will be mindful of where cloud computing can support a cohesive environment for users and developers, as well as understanding which challenges or uses it cannot meet.

Commercial public cloud can provide services such as access to scalable data storage and HPC, without up-front capital expenditure, with additional flexibility and the “pay as you go” model meaning a user or community only pay for what they need. The cost per unit of computation is higher within the commercial cloud but it converts large upfront capital cost into smaller incremental operational costs. It can also act as a proving-ground for certain workflows that can pave the way for repatriation of these to private cloud once ratified, thus saving money in the long term. Researchers can create a complex service by developing a combination of cloud-based computing

platforms and applications without the complexity of building and maintaining the underlying hardware and virtualisation layer infrastructure. To create and use cloud services it still requires considerable local people skills in terms of DevOps, HPC operations and application / user support. These support skills are often not provided by the public cloud and will be required to support users independent of where the workload is running. The nature of cloud computing whether public cloud or private cloud also enables shared adoption of community computing platforms and best practice and collaboration across a community, a key strength over institution-specific HPC. Cloud-like large-scale computing could also enable the hosting of curated datasets reducing the uploading and storage of duplicated data, enable users to have better support and orchestration for using containerised applications, and enable deployment of workloads that traditional HPC doesn't easily manage (Annex 3).

Public cloud computing is not suitable for all applications. In some cases, considerable expertise is required to use cloud services efficiently, and to not incur potentially sizeable unforeseen costs. While public cloud services can be cost effective, cost control needs careful consideration. Active monitoring and payment options for services or credits are typically billable by use and do not allow allocation caps. Therefore, they currently aren't suitable for analysis in the terabyte scale, so use/persistent storage of larger datasets and university data will often require expensive bespoke agreements that are similar or worse than cost-of-ownership for physical equipment. Potential costs mean opportunities for public cloud services are currently limited for larger scale research and careful consideration is important for planning their role in a research project or as a part of the wider DRI. Public cloud provision has a strong place within the UK DRI but has to be weighed against private UKRI funded public-sector clouds and of course there is still the need for people support skills independent of commercial or UKRI run cloud infrastructure.

Cloud computing has enabled a leap in the capacity to collaborate. In some disciplines, cloud-based tools are vital for participation in cutting edge research. Cloud computing enables collaborators to share data, tools and analysis of huge datasets, and is becoming increasingly important both national and internationally as data expands and becomes more multi-dimensional. Imaging collaborations are using cloud-computing for the development of novel methods, sharing data, visualisation techniques and analytics⁴⁷. Increasingly large international projects are using cloud-based collaboration, for example CERN openlab⁴⁸; the European Weather

Cloud⁴⁹ and Destination Earth Digital Twin⁵⁰ are creating Data Lakes and cloud infrastructure allied to exascale HPC (EuroHPC see Annex 3) resources and the deep-learning tool for microscopy analytics ZeroCostDL4Mic⁵¹ is also heralding not only cloud, but edge computing as part of the mix and an extension of hybrid cloud. Some communities have raised issues with cloud-based data sharing and storage policies for UKRI grants, particularly with regards to machine learning showing the importance of defining sovereignty.

The DRI environment should integrate national and local UKRI funded and run infrastructure together with commercial public clouds as a joined up federated research cloud, supporting the sharing of resources, data and applications across communities. To make the most of an integrated environment, infrastructure and cloud computing principles should include the need for resilient architecture to leverage different computing options, while maintaining portability and movement of software (interoperability) between platforms. Significant knowledge already exists within the National DRI, as mentioned above, as well as international efforts aiming to enable federation in cloud computing provide learning opportunities for the UK eco-system^{52, 53}. Training will be required to ensure users, operators and developers of cloud resources understand the cost implications, build-in interoperability with common APIs, and how this would need to be managed in terms of institutional or national budgets. For example, the DiRAC STFC national HPC service has been a long-term partner in the development and deployment of the UKRI Scientific OpenStack (SOS) and has developed a user and operator training for SOS which starts to address this need, although much more needs to be done. Also, as part of the UKRI SKA SRC project a UK SOS development and support team is being created to underpin the "develop one, use many, support one" principle enabled by the creation and use of a common community cloud middleware layer.

Recommendations

Recommendation 7: UKRI develop a strategy around the deployment, provision and use of centralised, local and commercial cloud research computing infrastructure as an integrated part of the UK's computing infrastructure

A considerable amount of experience and know-how, as evidenced above, is present in UKRI in the use and development of cloud computing technologies, both on and off-premises which can be harnessed. The Task Force advocated cross-UKRI coordinated strategy for cloud computing, informed by research councils, to support the provisioning of appropriate

and cost-effective research infrastructure. To facilitate this BBSRC and MRC would be responsible for understanding which bioscience applications cloud computing is most suited to, where it can and can't meet their communities' research needs, and where commercial cloud computing would and wouldn't be cost-effective. Public cloud computing should be considered as an optional part of a wider cohesive eco-system of local, national research cloud infrastructure. This should encompass a hybrid cloud model providing the appropriate interoperability and flexibility for the research community.

Integrating cloud computing should be fundamentally aligned to community needs, such as wider access to data management, flexible large-scale computing services, federation to enable researchers to make the best of their data, and web service hosting. It is also important to understand where cloud computing (in particular public cloud) may not be able to meet needs of the community in the computing eco-system, for instance sensitive or long-term storage of data, open-ended iterative development of algorithms or particularly intensive workflows that could incur costs above those in a local fair-use HPC environment. Cloud service expertise at national facilities should be leveraged by Research Councils to understand how researchers currently use systems and how this could be best provisioned to support research.

One key area would be whether UKRI's policy for cloud-based storage is facilitating research. International collaboration requires shared storage and analysis of data and policy should facilitate this collaboration, use of up-to-date methods and access to internationally recognised tools to support high quality grant applications and outputs from UK researchers. Building policy that supports innovation will enable UK communities to participate in international standard setting exercises, such as the Quarep-liMi initiative⁵⁴, enabling researchers to maintain and build new collaborations and access to cutting-edge tools.

3.4. Exascale

Theme summary, challenges, and implications for research

Research thrives on innovation and as the complexity of models or breadth and depth of data increases, communities have the potential to address previously unattainable questions, if they have access to appropriate resources. HPC systems can be made of millions of interconnected processor cores and which enable researchers to tackle much more challenging problems than possible on individual workstations or departmental systems. The UK scientific community

has had access to national HPC services since the 1980s with the first large-scale services appearing in the 1990s.

Work on the challenge of reaching the exascale (a supercomputer capable of sustaining over 10¹⁸ floating-point operations per second) began seriously in 2008. While the Japanese *Fugaku* system at Riken came close to the exascale in 2020 (0.44 Exaflop/s), the USA's *Frontier* system at Oak Ridge National Laboratory was the first internationally benchmarked system to demonstrate a sustained 1.1 Exaflop/s on the HPL benchmark. The USA has announced ambitions to build exascale five systems in total. Two exascale systems have also been reported in Chinese papers⁵⁵ but have not been formally announced¹⁴. By any measure, we have entered the exascale-age internationally. It should be noted that these first-generation exascale systems carry a cost premium in terms of capital and power with power cost in 2024/24 rising to £50M per year. Also, these current trail-blazing exascale systems have relatively low stability.

The UKRI position (on next phase of LSC investments¹⁵) is to develop a DRI strategy that recognises that UKRI's diverse research communities require LSC provision across a range of system sizes and architectures. Along with other leading research nations, the UK recognises the substantial opportunities that will arise from exascale systems, and the ambition is to provide exascale capability for the UK by the middle of this decade. UKRI's overarching priority is to provide appropriate and ambitious compute capabilities reaching out to exascale for UKRI's diverse research and innovation communities. To ensure that UKRI is prepared for future fiscal events, and opportunities beyond the Current Spending Review period, UKRI is leading on the preparation of two (strategic/outline) business cases:

- one focused on an exascale system targeting deployment by 2025;
- one focused on investment in large-scale accelerator-based compute capability for the UK over the next few years.

These cases, which will include exploration of options and costs associated with deployment, will be developed with the UKRI DRI Committee (DRIC) No decision has been taken at this stage. The selected project(s) will only proceed if funding has been identified, following endorsement by the UKRI Executive Committee and the necessary Governmental approvals.

Within the large-scale accelerator business case, the emphasis is on building a "Pathway to Exascale" via

the incremental deployment of federated exascale ecosystem consisting of a number of large (pre-exascale) systems of different technologies deployed across several UK supercomputing centres. This model of incremental iterative design and deployment cycles creating an exascale capability created by a federation of large but pre-exascale systems with a broad heterogeneous architecture in terms of technologies and workflows align well with emerging BBSRC / MRC strategy for fostering and developing its diverse LSC user community.

Large-scale compute is vital for pushing the boundaries and influential papers in some fields of biological and biomedical research, e.g. SARS-CoV2 virus simulations^{9, 10, 56} are already using exascale computing resources. Increasing amounts of HPC is needed to make the most of our evolving data landscape, including the Cryo-EM “resolution revolution”, linkage of health records, expanding biobanks, and processing of large scale well-described datasets for AI/ML. There is community consensus about a need to progress to exascale capability to produce internationally competitive research and provide an attractive environment for talented researchers. Furthermore, there are clear requirements for internationally competitive research infrastructure, particularly in light of Government ambitions to maintain and enhance the UK’s position as a science superpower⁵⁷.

The UK currently has 1.4 % of world’s HPC performance capacity³¹ (down significantly from 10.4 % in 2008) and has relied on programmes such as PRACE (EU) and Incite (USA) for access to the largest system world-wide over the past decade. The current national HPC service, ARCHER2, entered the Top500 at 22nd in the Nov 2021 list. Access to EU systems is now through the EU’s EuroHPC Joint Undertaking: UK applicants are only guaranteed, however, to be eligible through current H2020 funding. EuroHPC is co-purchasing HPC systems for the EU with member states. To date, three pre-exascale systems (each approximately 0.3 Exaflop/s have been procured). In June 2022, the EU’s first exascale service was announced. The JUPITER exascale Supercomputer service will be opened by FZ Jülich in Germany in 2024.

Biological and biomedical researchers in the UK use LSC, including Tier 2 HPC systems and ARCHER2 and are currently still able to apply to international systems through programmes such as INCITE and PRACE, although the larger research programmes using these international resources tend to be led by local researchers with UK participants acting as collaborators. Some crucial international partnerships have been damaged by Brexit. Compared to national resources using international resources does have

additional challenges including, flexibility of assigned time, accessing expertise to develop, install and optimise codes, familiarity with system architecture and access to expertise local to the resource.

UKRI provides a great opportunity for Research Councils to build coherent DRI supporting world-class national supercomputing infrastructure, including LSC services. However, investment must be planned, developed and implemented to fit user needs. All of the themes covered in this report are vital for building an exascale ecosystem that enables biological and biomedical science researchers to push the frontiers of research and to make the most of our world-class expertise.

Community building is a vital component of utilising digital research infrastructure, and ongoing efforts are required to determine the capability/capacity needs of the biological and biomedical communities as they develop over time. Greater capabilities should benefit all science, with increased efficiency of basic processes and broader access to petascale machines. Broader access to less powerful supercomputing is an important step towards exascale ambitions and HPC empowered communities can be leveraged for exascale projects in the longer term. Helping researchers understand the opportunities enabled by research computing, the barriers, and what they could be attempting next would help Councils understand the corresponding support mechanisms they need. Support should include access to RSE, technological, hardware or skills expertise.

Throughout the past decade, software and skills projects have been running in Japan, the USA, and the European Union in preparation for the exascale age. The UK’s computational science community, which is recognised as being world-class, engaged in many EU FP7 and H2020 projects until the end of H2020 but is now excluded from these activities. A number of EU Centres of Excellence have been formed, some with a specific focus on medical and biological science (CompBioMed⁵⁸, PerMedCoe⁵⁹ and BioExcel⁶⁰). Similarly, the US exascale Computing Project development includes the porting of codes and software integration to early exascale architectures, development of critical software capabilities to build a productive system and enable execution of applications and development of hardware to support the efficiency and reliability of an exascale system. The UKRI exascale Supercomputer project includes a large-scale software and skills programme. The UK’s ExCALIBUR programme¹⁶ seeks to understand and meet research software needs for exascale computing. This is an excellent step, but it is much smaller in scale and does not have the focus on international collaboration of EU activities.

Recommendations

Recommendation 8: UKRI, working with BBSRC and MRC should engage biological and biomedical research communities to understand current/ anticipated large-scale computing requirements and opportunities, including potential exascale class workload

The implementation of UKRI plans to deliver exascale computing capability should incorporate Research Council input to represent their communities during the development and preparation phases. Given its value to research, the Task Force recommended coordination between the UKRI Research Councils and their communities to understand the potential of much more powerful large-scale computing for the UK. The Implementation of the DRI Strategy for world-class national supercomputing infrastructure should consider what consultation/research is required to build a capability suitable for UK communities and what opportunities will be lost if the UK does not develop new facilities. In regard to developing large scale computing strategy and capability there exists

good opportunity for cross domain collaboration across all of UKRI and also outside of UK via interaction with the international exascale community.

The Task Force recommends the continuing development of national infrastructure, and identification of opportunities and challenges across the full spectrum of research computing users, across the whole UKRI remit. This would include immediate scientific and industrial challenges that could benefit from exascale capability, and how other communities could benefit from access to Petascale or Terascale computing. Consideration across the scale enables the development of support for different users and can help to strengthen communities who, while not currently ready to use computing at the largest scales, may be building towards the higher scales. Engaging communities on the opportunities can be used to develop the user requirements and unlock the next innovations in their fields. This needs to be developed throughout the planning and development phase, to build suitable resources and address barriers before the systems become available.

Humidity effects on droplets / aerosols

Lower humidity => droplets turn quickly into aerosols to reach farther and stagnate in air

Figure 4: Work from 2021 Gordon Bell special prize winner, using estimated virion inhalation to quantify the risk of infection under different environmental factors, including distance from an infected person, humidity and ventilation⁶¹. Bar graph summarises the relationship between relative humidity (RH) and the percentage of droplets ejected by a speaker reaching a person sat opposite, alongside images from simulations of droplet radius at different RHs.

3.6. Software

Theme summary, challenges, and implications for research

Computing has had profound impacts on bioscience research and is fundamental in many disciplines. In a survey of 417 Russell Group university researchers, 69% stated their work would be impossible without research software, and a further 21 % believe their work would more difficult⁶². The Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) recommends that a basic understanding of software development should be a ubiquitous requirement for researchers, similar to statistics or ethics, with additional training available as required⁶³.

Efficient use of large-scale computing, and cutting-edge scientific applications, require optimised software, often tailored to a specific application or system, with sustained support from an ecosystem of computational professionals, including developers embedded in research groups (for knowledge of specific applications), HPC software experts, computational scientists, research software engineers (RSEs), system architects and administrators³¹. As hardware is updated, new datasets created or architecture diverges, software must be constantly developed to run efficiently^{16,64}. Software is a vital consideration for many of the themes in this report. It should be obvious that computational research relies on good software. Perhaps less obviously, software is inherently tied to the recommendations we make under People, Skills and Training, particularly on career paths, because software development and maintenance requires specific and specialized expertise and skills.

Obtaining funding to develop and maintain software is often difficult. Relevant software development is within the remit of funding bodies, but cannot easily be assessed in competition against research grant applications, which are generally not good vehicles for development or maintenance of software^{65,66}. This can lead to software development by researchers without adequate training⁶² which can produce inefficient software of limited applicability. A focus purely on scientific applications in funding calls can discourage prioritising the optimisation, reproducibility and usability of software⁶⁷. Specific, distinct funding schemes are required for software development, maintenance and sustainability. Reports have also called for a culture shift to recognise software outputs in promotion and progression. There is also a need to develop the range of skills required to facilitate research, mechanisms to fund computational experts and support training and development^{39,13,31}.

The Collaborative Computational Projects (CCPs) bring together UK expertise in fields of research, including some in the biosciences, with funding

from several Research Councils. Some CCPs focus on scientific software development³⁷, e.g. CCP4 for structural biology.^{68,69} These and other similar activity provide examples of a collaborative approach, which can aid software development, e.g. by identifying emerging application areas and associated technical challenges⁷⁰.

Recommendations

Recommendation 9: BBSRC and MRC should work with other funders (including other UKRI research councils, Wellcome, CZI, Gates, Cancer Research etc) to create a cohesive framework supporting the life-cycle of software, including sustainability and maintenance, for biological and biomedical research

Research strategy should recognise the need for specific support for research software development, engineering and maintenance in bioscience. Existing mechanisms are not meeting software development sustainability needs. The development of software through research funding in the UK has typically been tied to specific research projects and lacks opportunities to develop and sustain code. There have been initiatives and calls for software development in the biosciences, which have been useful, but typically they have been relatively small in scale. Software sustainability and continued development is an essential part of the themes discussed in this report. The research ecosystem should support the development of new codes and innovation, and also consider the whole life-cycle of software, considering maintenance in proposals and providing funding opportunities to further develop and maintain codes, e.g., to improve usability, efficiency, robustness, scaling, development for new architectures, bug-fixing, extensibility or inter-operability. Collaboration with bodies such as the Software Sustainability Institute, Research Software Alliance Funders' Forum, community groups and research institutes could be leveraged to understand opportunities to develop a supportive ecosystem for software sustainability and maintenance, including optimal funding mechanisms and incorporation of FAIR principles for research software⁷¹.

There are some funding schemes aimed at the maintenance and development of existing research software^{72,73} but there is a clear need to go further: this is shown by feedback from bioscience research communities. Also, e.g. the 2021 round of the recently established EPSRC *Software for research communities* call had 145 applications⁷⁴, of which only 11 could be funded. This shows the significant demand for this type of funding.

The Task Force also highlighted the importance of UK participation in collaborative software

development and application. Development for new and emerging architectures should be a priority. Many computational techniques find application across different disciplines, and some code development will benefit from coordination between different scientific areas. We note also that cutting-edge scientific software development is often driven by applications, and application and development should go hand in hand, to ensure that developments meet bioscience research needs.

Recommendation 10: BBSRC and MRC should map exemplars and emerging software used by their communities/research areas

It is important to develop and maintain a knowledge base of how software is used in LSC across the biosciences. Mapping exemplars of current and emerging software and applications will provide a good evidence base to help understand how software is being used, how it was developed, funded and maintained, common challenges, opportunities for cohesion and service provisioning across communities. CCP projects related to the biosciences, and other similar networks and projects and expert groups should contribute to this mapping, and to maintaining a base of knowledge and expertise to inform BBSRC, MRC and UKRI.

An effective strategy to support software development for bioscience must consider the international context. The UK has led (and continues to lead) development of some internationally recognised, widely used bioscience research codes (e.g. the CCP4 integrated suite of programmes for structural biology, CCP-EM, RELION for cryo-EM structure determination and Fluctuating Finite Element Analysis). Development of many other leading codes (e.g. GROMACS⁷⁵, LAMMPS, AMBER and NAMD⁷⁶ for molecular dynamics) is led in other countries. Research software development, particularly of open source software, is international. Industry is also playing a role; for example, the deep learning application Enformer⁷⁷, which is used in gene expression prediction, developed by UK researchers at DeepMind. It is important that UK researchers are supported to participate in new and ongoing software development projects, including collaborative international projects which may be led outside the UK.

3.7. People, Skills and Training

Theme summary, challenges, and implications for research

World-leading research depends on innovation and creative thinking, and increasingly requires digital skills. Training needs in computational methods and techniques are apparent and growing across different

bioscience research communities. There is also basic need in training and awareness on accessing computational and data resources. Together, these form essential parts of a more cohesive environment.

Community engagement session organized by members of the Task Force showed growing need for support in accessing large-scale computing. HECBioSim reports increasing demands for support in the absence of local system administrative expertise and advocated greater access to expert support for the development and effective deployment of software (Annex 3). Users generally need to be engaged and informed on how to make the most of the developing ecosystem. Effective use of computing requires education and training to upskill bioscience researchers on what is available and how it can be used to address cutting-edge problems in bioscience.

A sustainable research environment must also support the career development of a broad range of researchers and professionals. While the UK has a strong reputation in large-scale computing, the career path for the highly skilled workers within academia and the public sector are not well defined, and private sector competition makes staff retention difficult³¹. Brexit has made recruitment and retention more difficult. Salaries for computational specialists in universities and research institutions generally are less competitive than those in the private sector in this area. Other challenges include progression and recognition, and temporary contracts³¹. Organisations such as EPSRC⁷⁸ and the Society of Research Software Engineering⁷⁹ have example initiatives attempting to address these challenges by professionalising skills such as software engineering and data management.

A review on data-intensive skills recommended the inclusion of clear guidance on the inclusion of professional support roles for data intensive grants¹³, while the MRC data science opportunities review recommended improvements to the improvements to the breadth and diversity of the people and skills as part of equitable teams, supported by attractive, dynamic, and sustainable biomedical data science career offers⁸⁰. The Task Force regarded professionalism of skills and representation of the important role they play in research a priority for biological and biomedical sciences. A deeper understanding of research communities requirements would help to define the training needs for users and developers, and opportunities for UKRI or research councils initiatives. Collaboration between domain scientists and RSE or computing professionals can help to build domain expertise, map scientific problems to computing solutions, build community understanding of large-scale computing skill

needs and produce efficient and reliable software. Understanding how this fits across different communities will avoid duplication, help shared learning and build cohesion.

Recommendations

Recommendation 11: BBSRC and MRC should engage their communities to understand requirements and develop a training strategy

The Task Force advocates the inclusion of People, Skills and Training as part of UKRI's DRI Strategy, to meet community needs and ensure expertise develops in parallel to computing infrastructure development. An empowered community can make the best use of resources and help to ensure we continue to generate internationally competitive research. To facilitate the UKRI Strategy, Research Councils should engage communities to maintain a deep understanding of their communities' needs around large-scale computing and associated people, skills and training. Examples of engagement include the MRC survey of data skills of early-mid career biomedical scientists and the UKRI DRI funded SSI survey on practices and barriers face when using software and computing in research. This is a rapidly evolving landscape, and a living strategy is required to understand short-term needs, carry out horizon scanning and understand upcoming changes for the community, for example access to new datasets, developments in computing architecture and what training will be required to make the most of these changes.

Research Councils need to recognise and address shortages in data and compute intensive research skills. Cross-UKRI coordination could support cohesion, best practice sharing, training, and bring together relevant cross council initiatives. The Task Force recommend that UKRI and Research Councils should support continued UK participation in the high-quality and diverse training, workshops, practical courses and networking opportunities provided by European and other international projects and bodies. Initiatives across Europe complement UK initiatives, such as the CCP projects, providing synergistic course material and cross-promotion to address training needs across communities, these include:

- NEUBIAS: Network of European BioImage Analysts
- European Molecular Biology Organization (EMBO)
- ELIXIR Europe
- CECAM
- BioExcel.

Recommendation 12: BBSRC and MRC should recognise and support the careers of computational experts in the research communities they represent

Developing the career offering for vital research skills will require sustained effort from research organizations and deserves consideration by UKRI. Investment is needed to support computational scientists and technical professionals, to developing sustainable career pathways. Software development, engineering and performance optimization requires a diverse ecosystem of qualified and skilled professionals: computing administrators/system managers, data managers/engineers, computational scientists and research software developers and engineers. Such professionals possess specialized skills, which are in significant demand in other sectors, and may not fit easily into traditional academic or administrative career paths in universities and research institutes: specific recognition is needed, including training, sustainable funding and environments that support career development and progression.

Better recognition of output/impacts, such as software developed, was a proposed lever to reward vital research staff and support their ability to pursue further projects. This should include expectations around the recognition of RSE's on applications and publications, rewarding time spent on research⁶³. The Australian Research Data Commons resource⁸¹ include guidance around making software citable and attribution and acknowledgement. The SSI resources⁸² include guidance on depositing software, sustainable development and publishing software. Better recognition requires coordinated efforts between Research Councils, other funding bodies and research organisations. Examples include including enabling Research Software Engineer applications for funding and recognition contribution or leadership roles in research, for example the BBSRC ALERT funding call was recently updated to accept applications from technical professionals and engineers.

An opportunity highlighted by the Task Force is improving cross-sector collaboration in bioscience research. There are excellent examples of research using large-scale computing involving industry and academia⁸³. UKRI, with Research Council representatives, could seek to understand how our communities currently work with industry, where further collaboration would be most beneficial, where barriers exist and how this could be enabled. Engagement initiatives, for example roundtables, could explore the experience of researchers and engineers and develop initiatives to support career pathways. These could initially map the career pathways of researchers moving across sectors,

seeking to understand the challenges and reduce barriers to collaboration with or movement into academia.

The Task Force and community engagement (e.g., Annex 4) highlighted significant structural challenges for some types of computational specialists working in research organisations, including precarious, short-term and piecemeal funding, alongside the difference in salary between academia and industry, making recruitment and retention difficult.

The career pathway for technical specialists and computational research specialists vs general university IT is still being developed. Building a sustainable work environment and meeting the UK's workforce needs will require continued efforts to refine the career pathway, status and expected role of research specialists. UKRI and research organizations should consider effects of salary differentials compared to the private sector, and other aspects of career development for computational experts.

3.8. Sustainability

Theme summary, challenges, and implications for research

Sustained funding for training, expertise, services and tools empowers communities to evolve, engage in complicated programmes of work and plan long term research projects. Response mode grant funding is excellent for enabling communities to drive the research agenda, however it doesn't provide the consistency required to maintain these vital research services. The uncertainty around funding is a challenge for service development/maintenance, long-term planning and attracting, supporting and retaining staff. The Task Force highlighted a lack of clarity around how critical digital research infrastructure resources should be sustainably funded, including which services were the responsibility of research councils and which were the responsibility of research organisations. There was also a lack of clarity around which Research Council funding opportunities could fund training, technical expertise, services and tool development/maintenance.

A stable environment for researchers provides the tools to innovate and push the boundaries in their area⁸⁴. The HECBioSim report surmises that longer-term funding of elements such as HPC allocations would enable better strategic planning of research activity. Block grants could be applicable to a range of projects providing more sustained funding (Annex 3). A stable environment should still facilitate the needs of cutting-edge research, and could be developed through the addition of long-term funding alongside responsive funding, aiming to provide sustained support for vital components of biological science research such operational costs, code, software and data.

Recommendations

Recommendation 13: UKRI aided by Research Councils should review and refine funding mechanisms to improve the sustainability of funding for core DRI

The Task Force recommended the development of more coherent and longer term funding mechanisms to provide consistent access to core resources, enabling researchers to plan long-term, reduce time spent bridging or finding funds for maintaining vital services and to prioritise innovative science.

Successfully implementing coherent funding requires an understanding of the underpinning support, skills and services required by different research communities. Scoping community needs should show how sustained funding can be implemented well, where there are gaps, how are these currently bridged and through what mechanisms. Working with Research Councils, we recommend that UKRI evaluate and plan greater coherence of funding mechanisms for underpinning support in computational science, including for software maintenance, development, engineering and sustainability. This should include allowance for sustained funding, minimizing "cliff-edge" drops in funding. Task Force suggestions include consistent low-level support or bridge funding for maintenance and infrastructure dedicated infrastructure teams tasked with facilitating continuous digital research infrastructure.

4. Horizon Scanning

Access to increased computing power enables experiments with a higher degree of complexity and use of more data intensive processes such as simulation, optimization, data processing and artificial intelligence. Not all biological and biomedical research areas have active LSC user communities, and may miss therefore miss opportunities to push the boundaries of research. Building understanding and coherency across communities can enable researchers to support each other and recognise the potential challenges across disciplines. The Task Force expects large-scale computing's impact on research to continue to grow over the next 5–10 years and highlighted some of the most promising areas.

Biosimulation is an excellent example of a community that has already excelled in harnessing emerging computing capabilities, revolutionising the scale of simulations and enabled key research, such as understanding coronavirus binding and infection mechanisms 1, 2. Looking forward the Task Force foresaw increasing complexity in simulation, greater use of machine learning to set up and steer biosimulation, minimising human contamination in problem solving, as well as convergent sampling of conformational space to allow quantitative prediction of binding free energies, assisting enzyme engineering, protein design and drug discovery⁸⁵.

Increasing standardisation and use of accessible data repositories will facilitate exploitation, AI and ML applications and more use of computing at all scales. The protein structure prediction tool AlphaFold 2 is an excellent example of how community data enabled a step change in the ability to model answers to a scientific problem;⁸⁶ this required enormous amounts of information from protein sequence databases and template structures⁸³. As research data sets grow, curation becomes ever more important and more difficult, requiring significant community coordination⁸⁷. It is widely recognised that effective curation is needed to get the best out of AI

applications and development. While some domains have established guidelines and standards for reporting data, development is needed in many areas of science⁸⁸. This is essential for the development of truly open science.

Access to friendly, standardized, usable data sets and project-based infrastructure will enable greater collaboration without relying on localized HPC or cloud resources. TREs have potential to be very powerful in facilitating collaborative access to data, with cloud bringing all of this together and acting as a lab bench to multinational efforts. Projects such as CLIMB-BIG-DATA are beginning to demonstrate the potential of virtual computational infrastructure for improving accessibility of large-scale computing applications⁸⁹.

The ever expanding repertoire of research data is accelerating the development of new tools for research. The Franklin Institute⁹⁰ is generating and disseminating knowledge of protein preparation, tissue localization, post translational modification and interactions in a biological environment. Hailed as the 'Resolution Revolution', the refinement of cryo-EM techniques enables researchers to gather atomic level detail from single particles, allowing structural biologists to examine large complexes and flexible molecules in much greater detail⁹¹, with significant implications for basic science, our understanding of disease and drug design. Standardised Clinical imaging databanks are being developed to facilitate research into diagnostics and treatment⁹². As advanced computing becomes more available and familiar, there will be applications in automation of sample collection and analysis, for example sensor-based data and microscopy, greater capacity to monitor and manipulate experimental, synthetic and analytical systems remotely, further contributing to the availability of datasets for research. All of these provide opportunities and challenges. The resulting increased understanding of biology allows researchers to innovate and ask new questions of data⁹³.

Building open libraries of existing application programming interfaces or functions can enable codes to be used as the building blocks for new research questions and long-term may make coding more accessible. Innovations such as the open AI codex⁹⁴ system aims to translate natural language into code and has the potential to provide new way for coding in research.

New datasets and computing capabilities also enable new combinations of data, linking data from different fields and different techniques for holistic understanding. Data on our physical environment has enormous potential for areas like agri-tech research, understanding organism adaptations to climate change, the incorporation of microbiome data into macroecology. This will improve understanding of how different elements of ecosystems interact and help answer research questions on pollution, ecology and pest phenotypes.

Digital research infrastructure enables new models of collaboration and research, for example the combination of experimental biologists and computational modelling in the 4D Nucleome (4DN) program to interpret genomic sequencing⁹⁵. DNA sequencing is a very powerful tool for understanding human disease, but there so much more can be done with this data. How DNA is arranged on the

chromosome, post-translational modifications, how translation, location or sequence can change are important in fully understanding disease. There is significant UK expertise in this area^{91, 92, 93, 95} and with right support this community could continue to be international leaders. Another example of new forms of collaboration enabled by DRI is through virtual reality, which allows interactive, real-time collaboration between researchers in different physical locations (e.g. using cloud). This includes, for example, applications of interactive VR in drug design⁹⁶. The potential of interactive VR for biodesign was demonstrated in the Covid pandemic: it was used to contribute to design and development of peptide inhibitors of the SARS-CoV-2 main protease (Mpro), for example: researchers in different physical locations worked together in a virtual environment to construct models of Mpro complexes⁹⁷.

Improved digital research infrastructure, access to LSC and specialist hardware, alongside the increasing depth and breadth of datasets will continue to provide transformative opportunities for biological and biomedical research communities¹³. These increased capabilities and growing expertise in research communities will enable them to tackle previously unattainable research questions and act as a stepping-stone to the next generation of innovation.

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Annex 1

Task force member affiliations

Member	Affiliations
Dr Sarah Butcher	Leads a team at the European Bioinformatics Institute responsible for the development, adaption and operation of software to support the ever-evolving needs of biological data service operators and users. Collaborators include the Human Cell Atlas, BioExcel 2 and ELIXIR implementation studies.
Dr Paul Calleja	The Director of the Cambridge Centre for Data-Driven Discovery, an interdisciplinary research centre bringing together researchers and expertise from across the academic departments and industry to drive research into the analysis, understanding and use of data science and AI. Paul is founding member of the UK High Performance Computing Special Interest Group and a member of the Tier-2 Directors group.
Dr Neil Chue Hong	Holds a Personal Chair in Research Software Policy and Practice at the University of Edinburgh, and is the PI and Founding Director of the Software Sustainability Institute, a national facility for research software users and developers whose mission is to cultivate better, more sustainable, research software to enable world-class research. Neil is on the Board/Panel for numerous initiatives including ExCALIBUR, Research Software Alliance, BBSRC TTSAP, STFC PPTAP and FAIR4RS.
Professor Rob Davey	Head of e-Infrastructure and leads the Data Infrastructure and Algorithms Group at Earlham Institute Group, researching how best to manage, represent and analyse data for open science, and exploring new hardware, algorithms and methodologies to develop tools to push the boundaries of data-driven informatics in the life sciences.
James Fleming	The Chief Information Officer at the Francis Crick Institute. The IT Department under him is responsible for the IT infrastructure, high-performance computing and three public clouds, enabling CRICK researcher collaborations with 1,400 institutions across 90 countries. James is on the Board for the MRC's DSAG and UKRI's Infrastructure and Capital Advisory Group and Digital Research Infrastructure Advisory Group.
Professor Andrew French	Research's bioimage analysis at the University of Nottingham, developing novel AI and computational methods to extract data from biological images. He has expertise in both computer vision and deep learning approaches to image analysis, with a strong focus on AI technique development.
Professor Sarah Harris	Research at the University of Leeds focused on the use of high performance computing to model biomacromolecules and their interactions using the physics of macromolecules. This research combines biophysical tools, including theory and computation, and a strong collaborative research community. Sarah is part of the core development team for the mesoscale modelling tool "Fluctuating Finite Element Analysis" and Chairs CCPBioSim.

Member	Affiliations
Professor Emily Jefferson (Deputy Chair)	Chief Technology Officer (CTO) of Health Data Research UK seconded from her position as the Director of the Health Informatics Centre (HIC) at the University of Dundee. Emily leads the development and delivery of technology services to enable the provision of consistent and meaningful research access to health data and will lead the next stage of development which will include collaborating with Trusted Research Environment providers across the UK on federated analytics.
Professor Syma Khalid	Department of Biochemistry, University of Oxford. She develops and applies computational models to establish an atomistic-level understanding of bacterial cell envelope organisation and function, and to aid the design of synthetic systems such as nanopores for applications in bionanotechnology. Syma is the current chair of HECBioSim and the Technical Advisory Panel of the Artificial Intelligence and Informatics theme of the Rosalind Franklin Institute.
Professor Nick Loman	Professor of Microbial Genomics and Bioinformatics, Institute for Microbiology and Infection, University of Birmingham. His research explores the use of cutting-edge genomics and metagenomics approaches to the diagnosis, treatment and surveillance of infectious disease. Nick is a co-investigator on the £8.4m Cloud Infrastructure for Microbial Genomics (CLIMB) project to invest in bioinformatics and 'big data' capacity building for the UK community.
Dr Gail McConnell	Director of the Centre for Biophotonics at the University of Strathclyde and leads the Strathclyde Theme of Physics and Life Sciences. Her research involves the development of new optical instruments and technologies for cell and tissue imaging: this includes linear and nonlinear optics, new light sources, and new ways of preparing the specimen for imaging that reveals more structural information than the light microscope can normally provide.
Professor Adrian Mulholland (Chair)	Director of Research, School of Chemistry, University of Bristol and ERC Advanced Grant holder. His research focuses on computational biochemistry, including modelling enzyme catalysis, antibiotic resistance mechanisms, protein design and protein-ligand binding. Adrian was founding Chair of HECBioSim (2013–18) and CCPBioSim (2010–20), and was Chair of the CCP Steering Panel (cross-Research Council Panel overseeing UK Collaborative Computational Projects) (2016–20). He is a Member of the EPSRC Science, Technology and Engineering Board (SETB). He was a Member of the BBSRC Appointments Board (2019–22); Chair, Steering Group, UK Catalysis Hub (2018–21). Awarded John Meurig Thomas Medal 2020.
Professor Sebastien Ourselin	Head of the School of Biomedical Engineering & Imaging Sciences at King's College London and Director of the Wellcome/EPSCRC Centre for Medical Engineering and Deputy Director of the London Medical Imaging and Artificial Intelligence Centre for Value Based Healthcare. Sebastien has significant experience in translating and commercialising healthcare technology.
Professor Mark Parsons	Personal Chair in High Performance Computing at the University of Edinburgh and Director of EPCC, the University of Edinburgh's supercomputing centre. The EPCC is the leading supercomputing centre in the UK and hosts and manages many of the UK's national High Performance Computing and Research Data services, including the hosting and management of the Scottish National Data Safe Haven. Mark is on the Board for the MRCs DSAG.

Annex 2

Examples of DRI community engagement

Table 1: Examples of digital research infrastructure engagement initiatives and opportunities including biological and biomedical research communities

Title	Description
Software and Skills for Large-Scale Computing: collecting evidence to develop a <u>National Research Software Strategy</u>	This SSI study, funded by EPSRC to inform the UKRI DRI strategy implementation, is collecting evidence to develop a National Research Software Strategy. This study included a survey, promoted through BBSRC and MRC stakeholders alongside other councils, on the practices and barriers that UK researchers face when using software and computing in their research, which communities are using which infrastructure and how this changes as they go through their career.
<u>UK AI Research Infrastructure Requirements Review</u>	This review is being undertaken by Technopolis, on behalf of The Alan Turing Institute and UKRI. The study includes a survey about current and future needs in relation to compute, data access and skills for AI research and innovation in the UK.
The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC), (previously part of the EU FP7 projects and H2020 HPC programmes).	This joint initiative between the EU, European countries and private partners, supports the development of user-driven large-scale computing infrastructure, HPC skills, innovative computing systems and services. As key parts of many EuroHPC projects, they have been one of the world's largest sustained investors in developing and optimising HPC software and community building over the past decade.
<u>The Exascale Computing Project</u>	This initiative run by the U.S. Office of Science (SC) and the National Nuclear Security Administration (NNSA), seeks to work in partnership with government, academia, and industry to build a suitable exascale computing ecosystem. This includes a coordinated programme of research on community needs for application development, software technology, hardware and integration.
Engagement with community representatives. These include <u>High End Computing (HEC) Consortia</u> and <u>UK Collaborative Computational Projects</u>	Working with groups representing and engaging with researchers can bring together a range of views from experts and capture the wider views of a community. The HECBioSim consortium report on 'biomolecular simulations' (Annex 3) brings together information on the demand and needs of the community, summarising information from their annual reports, the views of stakeholders, industry engagement and outreach activities.

Title	Description
Research Council Community specific engagement	Community engagement or outreach events can be used to speak directly to and build a granular understanding of a community needs. The meeting report in Annex 4 is a summary of discussion with representatives of the biophysics and biosimulation community on their computing needs, including the associated training/skills, software and services, challenges, gaps and barriers to the use of computing and research opportunities that could be facilitated by access to larger scale computing capability.
Research computing resources insights from Research Council strategic Institutes <u>1</u>, <u>2</u>	Insight from and engagement with centres of excellence or strategically funded institutes can reveal existing uses of large-scale computing in sample communities as well as anticipated needs. This could include drawing on expertise drawing on biological and biomedical science expertise to inform implementation of UKRI DRI for specific infrastructure, for example cloud computing, research areas, for example genomics, or centre insight into the computing requirements of their researchers (see Annex 5).

Annex 3

HECBioSim consortium report

HECBioSim consortium report on computing usage and needs of biomolecular simulations researchers

Authors – Syma Khalid (Oxford) HECBioSim chair, Sarah Harris (Leeds) CCPBioSim chair

Background

This report was written based on consultations with users of Tier 1 and Tier 2 HPC facilities in the remit of biomolecular simulation via the HECBioSim consortium (HECBioSim.ac.uk). HECBioSim allocates resources on ARCHER2 and a range of Tier 2 facilities via competitive assessment of project proposals. The HECBioSim Management Group has a good grasp of the demand and needs across the biomolecular simulation community (and links to a wide range of experimental and industrial collaborators, and access to data on usage and (via our annual reports) also details of publications, industry engagement and outreach activities.

Hardware

A balance between HPC capability and capacity is essential to meet the range of needs and challenges across biosimulation and associated fields. There are clear research needs for large-scale compute (e.g. high impact publications on SARS-CoV-2 virus simulations on which UK scientists were authors, but the lead authors were most often based in other countries due to opportunity offered by exascale outside of the UK) – greater ambition within the UK funding system to enable large/long simulations would enable researchers to host internationally exemplar research. This is important because “headline-grabbing” work is absolutely vital in a world where different research communities are competing with each other for investment. Moreover, the ‘resolution revolution’ in cryo-EM, which has seen a huge increase in the size of biomolecular complexes whose structures can be solved at atomic resolution, provides new opportunities for multidisciplinary studies, but in order to do so, simulation system sizes are also increasing proportionally, requiring increasing amounts of HPC time.

There is significant and growing need for GPUs for simulation, ML and AI applications. The UK biomolecular simulation community noted that ARCHER2 does not provide GPU capability: the UK lacks Tier 1 HPC GPU capability. GPUs are available via UKRI Tier 2 facilities, which are now accessible across different Council remits. At the time of the

original consultation, it was noted that 7 of the top 10 supercomputers in the world feature GPU solutions. With deep learning increasingly permeating biological and biomedical research, there is a growing need for hardware able to train models on a scale that can compete with cutting-edge machine learning (ML) work in other countries. Getting the community more used to these technologies will be beneficial in the long run, especially because any serious exascale contenders are likely to be GPU based. The biomolecular simulation community does however also require access to more traditional CPU based HPC for those doing things that are not yet available in a GPU ported form. Thus the split on national Tier1 (CPU) vs Tier2 (GPU) could be split more in favour of the GPUs if the equivalent amount of resource time could be found, at a community level, the biomolecular simulation community is one of the most prolific and heaviest consumers of GPU time (data available via HECs).

A cloud-like approach using traditional HPC with cloud-like orchestration could be a real strength for some applications; ML in particular. This could open up lots of possibilities such as curated data sets on high performance NVMe disks, this would stop lots of users uploading the same datasets (ref alphafold) over and over, it would enable users to have better support and orchestration for using containerised applications and they would be able to deploy the sorts of workloads that traditional HPC cannot easily manage. There is a huge requirement on system administrators to modernise their skillset to actually deliver this, so this would also need investment (either new staff or training existing ones). We note that a cloud-like arrangement would also likely lead to reduced queuing time to run calculations.

Through HECBioSim we have seen that for the services we currently operate, the greater the diversity of architectures, the more support the community needs to extract value and performance from them, the support requirements are likely the heaviest of the HEC communities. Often local sys. admins do not have a good understanding on how to get the performance out of the newer architectures, this is

where HECBioSim and Cospec support have been increasingly stepping in (particularly with JADE/2 and Bede) and this the need for this is likely to increase if we onboard more Tier2 GPUs. Many within our community are continually voicing the need for improved RSE and related expert support both for developing software and for deploying it effectively on national HPC.

Lack of access to long-term storage has limited the length and size (and therefore ambition) of many simulation projects within the community and also limits wider use of the data including exploitation via AI and ML. Appropriate storage is an essential component of any HPC-based project and thus should not be considered an 'add on' – it is integral to the day to day running of projects and also ensuring their longevity.

Resource allocation

There is an overwhelming feeling throughout the biomolecular simulation community that the HEC model works well. HECBioSim operate a policy of "supportive peer review", where proposals are given feedback, and resubmissions approved once the proposal meets the required standards. Small amounts of time are regularly awarded to help PIs establish new, ambitious projects. However, it has been pointed out that longer-term funding would enable better and more strategic planning of research activities. A suggested model is annual or biennial block grants which the PI could apply as needs be for a whole range of projects. This could even be something like the crystallographers 'bag' e.g. on

an institutional basis. The size of the allocation would match the scale of the projects, and it could be renewed/scaled down/cancelled on the basis of an annual report of outputs. This would enable longer term planning – i.e. knowing one had a certain amount of HPC allocation for the next 18 months and not having to come up with specific projects every 6 months or so to top up the allocation (the latter is the case within the HEC model).

HPC still appears to be perceived as being firmly in the EPSRC remit, whereas in reality it is highly important for medical, biotechnology and biochemical research (as evidenced by the number of top papers using HPC that emerge from these communities). This perception is reflected in fact that the notional costs for Archer are higher for BBSRC and MRC grants compared to EPSRC.

In consultation with:

- Julien Michel (Edinburgh)
- Mark Sansom (Oxford)
- Philip Biggin (Oxford)
- Shozeb Haider (UCL)
- Phillip Stansfeld (Warwick)
- Carmen Domene (Bath)
- Francesco Gervasio (UCL)
- Arianna Fornili (QMUL)
- Franca Fraternali (King's College)
- Charles Laughton (Nottingham)
- Adrian Mulholland (Bristol)
- James Gebbie (STFC)

Annex 4

Biophysics and biosimulation community event report

Biophysics and biosimulation large-scale computing community engagement

Notes from meeting 10th June 2022

Background

In 2021, the MRC Data Science Strategic Advisory Group (DSAG) and BBSRC Transformative Technologies Strategy Advisory Panel (TTSAP) endorsed the formation of a large-scale computing Task Force. This Task Force aims to support BBSRC and MRCs granular understanding of their communities computing needs, including the associated training/skills, software and services, to inform the development and implementation of a strategy for investment and support in this area.

Task Force recommendations included community-specific engagement and the secretariat worked with Task Force members to develop events.

These notes capture discussion from the first of these events, chaired by Sarah Harris (Astbury Centre, University of Leeds) on 10/06/2022, with members of the biophysics and biosimulation community to:

- better understand current usage of computing in their research and their future needs
- explore the challenges, gaps and barriers to the use of computing, and the opportunities for the more effective use of existing capability
- identify challenging research concepts/areas and the associated computing requirements and whether these could be enabled by access to larger scale computing capability

The engagement event was publicized through CCPBioSim (<https://www.ccpbiosim.ac.uk/>), CCP-EM (<https://www.ccpem.ac.uk/>), CCP4 (<https://www.ccp4.ac.uk/>), CCP-N (<https://ccpn.ac.uk/>), CompBioMed (<https://www.compbiomed.eu/>) and MRC university/ Centre/Unit contacts. Prior to the event, invitees were asked to complete a brief survey and during the event attendees were split into break out rooms and asked to consider discussion prompts.

The notes below do not capture the meetings verbatim, but seek to draw out key themes from attendee discussion. The precursory sections in italics provide context around the meeting discussion.

Notes from the event

Session 1: Current Needs & Challenges

Computing has transformed bioscience research and is now fundamental in many disciplines. A recent analysis of BBSRC's funding portfolio found > 50 % of grants now involve large-scale data, encompassing sequencing, omics, imaging, and other data intensive platforms requiring mathematical and computational analysis. In this session attendees discussed the challenges of using research computing and potential opportunities.

Challenges accessing computing resources is impeding the community's capacity to undertake science

Challenges relating to accessing resources and hardware were common during the discussion and preceding survey. 14 of 31 survey responses referenced this issue, including availability of sufficient HPC resources, both locally and nationally, cost-effective data storage post-simulation and network bandwidth.

Attendees discussed the huge demands on and limited availability of National Supercomputing Services and local computation resources in the UK, and the difficulties that this creates in achieving internationally competitive science. Availability of HPC and GPU capabilities in the UK were both cited as challenges. Access difficulties are impacting users seeking to develop new research opportunities and those pioneering HPC in science, any strategy seeking to improve the availability of resources should consider users across this range of small to large scale. Researchers working on high end applications of computing require a heterogeneous environment encompassing resources suited to small- and large-scale applications.

Greater coordination of resources and underpinning support could improve efficiency

Attendees discussed the challenges of working across multiple facilities and services, benefits of coordination to make the most of local, regional and national resources and bring greater value to UKRI in the development and structuring of this

eco-system. Astronomy was cited as a good example of community collaboration. Coordinated infrastructure should seek to understand opportunities to improve efficiency across the ecosystem, such as resource sharing, training and the role of cloud computing.

A greater emphasis on process optimization at earlier stages of requesting resources could reduce demand and alleviate some of access challenges. This would use computing resources more efficiently, however enabling this optimisation would rely on access to local resources, expertise and machines to develop codes or methods, benchmark programmes and support scaling as a project develops.

The community's scientific progress is not being matched by the availability computing resources

The increased scale of data collection and data available for research needs to be matched by hardware. The expense of upgrading resources was seen as a barrier. Such upgrades are needed to meet the community's ambitions and costs should be considered against the impact of reduced opportunity for research. The availability of data storage is restricting what data can be retained, impacting reproducibility and open science, and restricting opportunities e.g. in ML. Network speed in the UK can hinder the feasibility of sharing datasets and collaborating on science. There are opportunities to invest in data storage and community driven efforts to standardise, organise and make the most of collected data. Some of the hardware challenges could be addressed through investment in the UK, for example investment in UK semiconductor companies to begin tackling shortages in key hardware components.

Realising the UKs FAIR data and open science ambitions requires suitable infrastructure

As our ambitions and data sets grow, the capacity to store and make underpinning raw data available is an increasing challenge. While researchers are facing issues with data storage, this is a live issue, and the UK Government Science and Technology Committee is undertaking an inquiry into reproducibility and research integrity. UK experimental facilities need the capacity to store data measured/processed and meet community best practice. For example, the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility, Institut Laue Langevin, ISIS Neutron facilities all issue citable data DOIs, while Diamond Light Source currently does not.

The existing eco-system makes it challenging to recruit and retain personnel with the computing skills required for research

Challenges relating to skills and training were commonly cited during discussion and preceding survey. 11 of 31 survey responses referenced this issue, including workforce computational skills, knowledge and experience.

Attendees discussed the challenges relating to workforce skills and retention. The breadth of undergraduate courses are not equipping students with the computing skills required by bioscience research, putting more burden on research groups to develop and maintain biologists with the skills they need. Developing personnel is rewarding and an important part of integrating people into a field, however the surrounding environment makes it challenging to retain developed staff. The career pathway for some skilled staff, such as Research Software Engineers (RSEs) and technical IT specialists, isn't well-defined in academia, with the organisational restrictions around salaries, career progression, job security and satisfaction considered key challenges. These skills are often highly valued in other sectors, with higher salaries and better-defined career pathways, providing an external pressure that exacerbates staff retention. Some of these challenges could be alleviated in the short-term through flexible working conditions that facilitate part time, remote working, use of global expertise and commitment from Universities to embed specialist positions, such as RSEs, in subject departments instead of in central IT departments, but these issues should be considered as part of a wider computing infrastructure strategy.

A skilled workforce is vital for internationally competitive research

Shortages in computational science, system management, advanced computing and software development skills impacts the productivity and capabilities of research. Specialists who manage HPC clusters report having to spend more time teaching rudimentary skills to new users, reducing their capacity for other elements of their role. RSE expertise is required to optimise codes for efficient use of HPC, and there are significant shortages in the availability of these research critical functions. Recent examples using HPC to push the boundaries of biological research required years of software engineering from experienced professionals integrated in the project, building on the foundations of community coding expertise.

Funding in the UK should adapt to meet the community's software requirements

Current funding mechanisms are not well suited to support the software needs of the biomolecular simulation community, and associated interdisciplinary work. There are gaps in the availability of funds for underpinning needs such as software development, maintenance and visualisation activities. Typically, software funding in the UK has been tied to scientific advances and without domestic opportunities to maintain and sustainably develop code researchers are often reliant on internationally

developed codes. Recently there have been positive steps to facilitate software development, engineering and maintenance, such as the 'EPSRC Software for research communities' call. For this call, EPSRC reported 145 applications to this panel in 2021, of which only 11 could be funded, demonstrating a significant interest in and need for this type of funding, and unmet demand for research software development support. There is a growing need for software development support in the biomedical and life sciences domains.

Operational expenditure was also cited as a challenge. While there are clear paths to request capital investment, operational expenditure is less clear. The maintenance of local resources often relies on small funds from associated research grants to sustain them.

Session 2: Future Needs and Aspirations

As the depth and breadth of datasets and computing power grows, biosimulation and biophysics are in an excellent position to pioneer the use of research computing and harness these growing capabilities. Key research to understand COVID-19 relied on simulation using some of the world's most powerful computing resources (1, 2). In this session, attendees discussed their computing needs in the short to medium term and research aspirations.

The community's scientific ambitions require greater access to research computing, and infrastructure development informed by user needs

Further investment in research computing and access to resources to enable data intensive workflows was a common theme in the meeting and survey responses. Biomedical, life science and biology research increasingly requires a heterogenous compute infrastructure. This will need transparent long-term planning, with more dedicated GPU clusters for specialist applications; access to HPC with a variety of architectures; access to cloud computing; coordinated local and national facilities; greater access to data storage and better networking facilities. There are opportunities for UKRI to develop a long-term strategy and coordinate infrastructure including priorities such as training and knowledge sharing across research areas. Ideally this would include clear systems for researchers to communicate their needs and challenges with UKRI, potentially through engagement with High-End Computing Consortia and Collaborative Computational Projects.

The community would like greater clarity on what is currently available and how it can be best used

Attendees reflected on the importance of coordination across resources and support for researchers. Tools, guidance or services to understand what computing resources are available in the UK – which of these would best suit a researcher's needs, how these can be accessed, how can codes or simulations be optimised to help researchers make the best use of their time and improve accessibility of research computing. Ideally, researchers should be able to access infrastructure, software support and professional support to develop projects for local machines, and where appropriate scale these up to higher tier HPC.

Well funded and coordination resources could enable researchers to spend less time on administration and more time on science

Resource distribution should fit community needs for heterogenous, distributed facilities, supported by a variety of access modes. This would require operational funds to support the facility management and users, and has the potential to add value through more efficient use of machines. Increased efficiency should not drive out the flexibility and autonomy that enables the community to drive innovation. There may be opportunities to integrate across computing resources, including unified log-in, access, allocation of resources, data storage, data sharing capability to support equitable access and infrastructure planning.

Future funding initiatives could support responsive mode style applications and larger collaborative projects involving both computational and experimental scientists. National computing resources could be accessed centrally through UKRI, with equivalent costs across research communities.

Attendees discussed their research aspirations for the future as access to increased computing power enables a higher degree of complexity and data intensive processes:

- An empowered research community with the skills required to use HPC resources as simply as they currently use desktop resources.
- A joined-up ecosystem, in which UK High-End Computing Consortia and Collaborative Computational Projects act to connect communities and UKRI to promote synergistic engagement and collaboration.
- Engagement with modelling expertise outside of biosimulation, building on expertise and supporting the interface between communities

- Enabling simulations to talk to each other and begin connecting atomic level physics and chemistry to large scale biological functions
- Additional complexity to enable bigger simulations with longer time scales and larger molecules. Such models would interrogate biological function in complex environments, contributing to understanding of pathogens, drug design and synthetic biology.
- Connecting molecular, cellular, organ and organism level information, understanding the opportunities to unite learnings from reductionism and system level research.
- Applying simulations to understand biosynthesis pathways and develop therapeutics for human diseases, such as novel antimicrobial and anti-viral agents.
- Virtual organisms as disease models to solve health issues and improve preventative medicine. This could include simulating critical processes such as cell division or axoneme function or mapping complex organs like such as the brain's neural circuitry.

Annex 5

Crick Insititute Research computing resources

Insight from internal reporting, courtesy of James Fleming Director of Information Technology and Services. An approximate indication of the range of compute resources required to support research at the Francis Crick Institute, as of December 2022. For ~1800 researchers covering most disciplines of biological/biomedical research, the Crick Institute requires:

- ~3500 laptops, workstations & tablets
- 3 supported operating systems – Windows, MacOS, Linux
- 2 internal networks – one standard LAN, one Infiniband high speed data transfer
- 168 applications to run the institute including specialist systems like mouse colony management
- ~850 Virtual Machines running lab systems and custom science databases
- A CPU VM platform on premises
- A GPU VM platform on premises
- A 11,500 core CPU HPC cluster
- 3 GPU HPC clusters – 64 node visual analytics, 160 node general workload, 64 node highest performance for complex informatics and deep learning
- 24PB high speed storage (when the Crick was built 7 years ago, 3PB was the original spec, and deemed to be future proof)
- 20PB tape library with dual-site resilience for backup and archive, scalable to 250+PB)
- AWS, Azure and GCP virtual data centres running a variety of workloads
- Custom Snowflake TRE platform
- SFTP high speed data transfer service